

Density functional based reactivity studies on aziridinium ion intermediates

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Abstract : Reactivities of the aziridinium ion intermediates of six anticancer drugs belonging to the nitrogen mustard family are analysed using conceptual density functional theory based reactivity descriptors. Reactivity of the species is found to depend on dielectric of the solvent. Enthalpy, Gibbs energy and entropy of formation of aziridinium ions are analysed at different temperatures and solvents at B3LYP/6-31+G(d) level of theory. Further, the natural bond orbital (NBO) analysis is performed which seemed to be quite informative.

Keywords : DNA cross-linking agents, aziridinium ion, DFT based reactivity descriptors, solvent medium.

Introduction

Nitrogen mustards represent the earliest and perhaps the most extensively studied DNA inter-strand cross-linking agents and is being used in cancer chemotherapy for more than five decades^{1,2}. This class of drug molecules form a positively charged reactive aziridinium ion (Az^+) intermediate which is unstable and reacts easily with cellular biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, proteins etc.³. Cytotoxicity of these drug molecules is attributed to their alkylation with the nucleophilic ability centres of the DNA bases and N7 position of guanine is the most preferred site, forming mono- and cross-linked adducts⁴. It was also reported that the alkylation occurs preferentially at the endocyclic nitrogen and exocyclic oxygen atoms of the DNA bases^{5,6}. In an important work, Shukla *et al.* used quantum mechanical calculations to observe the interaction of mustine molecule with different DNA bases⁷. Mustine, the most primitive and extensively employed nitrogen mustard is the most reactive one. Because of its high reactivity, more stable analogues were sought and substitution of its methyl group by electron withdrawing groups make the nitrogen atom less nucleophilic which slows down the rate of Az^+ ion formation, in turn reducing reactivity⁸. Chlorambucil, melphalan, spiromustine, uracil mustard, bendamustine are some example of such analogues (Fig. 1). Despite being a potent anti-tumour agent, these drug molecules suffer a major drawback that limit their clinical application is that these drugs are not

Fig. 1. Structures of few clinically used nitrogen mustards.

cell specific i.e. apart from cancerous cells, they attack other normal cells of the body and hence obstruct DNA replication and transcription^{1,3,4}. Thus stability/reactivity of the Az^+ ion is important during alkylation process.

Earlier, it was shown that reactivity of Az^+ ion is affected by different factors such as solvent, external electric field, configuration of the species etc.⁹.

DFT based reactivity descriptors such as global hardness, chemical potential, global electrophilicity etc. are efficient tools to describe the reactivity pattern of chemical species^{10,11}. These descriptors have been tested and studied by several research groups and are found to be very useful in rationalizing the reactivity patterns of the molecular systems and reviewed well¹².

In the present work, we considered six nitrogen mustards (Fig. 1) and studied reactivity of their corresponding Az^+ ions using DFT based reactivity descriptors. Global reactivity descriptors specifically global hardness (η) and global electrophilicity (ω) are calculated in gas phase as well as in three different solvent phases (ranging from polar to non-polar). Apart from that, interaction energy between Az^+ ion intermediates and GC base pairs have been observed. Further, NBO analysis is performed with the same level of theory.

Theoretical details of reactivity descriptors and computational details :

In DFT, chemical potential (μ) is defined as the first derivative of energy with respect to the number of electrons¹³ :

$$\mu = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (1)$$

and global hardness (η)¹⁴ as :

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (2)$$

where, E is the energy and N is the number of electrons of an electronic system at constant external potential, $v(\vec{r})$.

In most of the applications, chemical potential (μ) and chemical hardness (η) are calculated using finite difference approximation in terms of IP and EA which leads to the working formulae

$$\mu = \frac{-(IP + EA)}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta = \frac{(IP - EA)}{2} \quad (4)$$

Use of Koopmans' theorem¹⁵ defines the IP and EA in terms of the energies of highest occupied molecular orbital (ϵ_{HOMO}) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (ϵ_{LUMO}) as :

$$IP = -\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}} \quad (5)$$

$$EA = -\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} \quad (6)$$

and therefore, μ and η can be expressed as :

$$\eta = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\mu = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} + \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (8)$$

Parr and co-workers proposed global electrophilicity (ω) as a measure of electrophilicity of a ligand¹⁶ as :

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} \quad (9)$$

It is the measure of capacity of a species to accept an arbitrary number of electrons.

The gas phase geometrical minima of the species are optimized using 6-31+G(d) basis set with Becke three parameter exchange and Lee, Yang and Parr correlation functional, B3LYP¹⁷ and confirmed by frequency calculation. Geometry optimization is followed by single point calculations at the same level of theory at different temperatures (ranging from a low to high value, 77 to 315 K) and in three different solvents (*n*-octanol, $\epsilon = 9.86$, 1,2-ethanediol, $\epsilon = 40.24$ and water, $\epsilon = 78.35$), using polarizable continuum model (PCM)¹⁸. The dielectric constant of the fluids in different parts of human body are different, varying from non-polar to a polar one and hence three solvents having a range of dielectric constant are chosen. The global reactivity descriptors (chemical potential, global hardness and global electrophilicity) are calculated using eqs. (7)–(9). All calculations are performed using Gaussian09¹⁹.

Results and discussion

Variation of reactivity descriptors :

The reactivity/stability of corresponding aziridinium ion intermediates is monitored using global hardness and global electrophilicity values. The gas phase hardness and electrophilicity were calculated at B3LYP/6-31+G(d) level

of theory. Further to realize the effect of solvents on the reactivity pattern, we repeat our calculations in three different solvent media at the same level of theory, variations are shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b).

(a) Global hardness

(b) Global electrophilicity

Fig. 2. Variation of electrophilicity (eV) and hardness (eV) of the aziridinium ions from gas to aqueous phase (■—gas phase, ●—*n*-octanol, ▲—1,2-ethanediol, ▼—water).

In gas phase, the hardness order is : mustine > spiromustine > chlorambucil > uracil mustard > bendamustine > melphalan and changes to mustine > spiromustine > chlorambucil > uracil mustard > melphalan > bendamustine in aqueous phase. On the

other hand electrophilicity is in the order : uracil mustard > spiromustine > melphalan > chlorambucil > bendamustine > mustine in gas phase and uracil mustard > melphalan > bendamustine > chlorambucil > spiromustine > mustine in aqueous phase. It is important to note that, as we move from gas phase to a solvent phase, hardness of the Az⁺ ions do not change much (Fig. 2(a)). Contrarily, electrophilicity shows a dramatic drop in their values (on moving from gas phase to *n*-octanol), indicating low reactivity of the Az⁺ ions in solvent phases, Fig. 2(b). With further increase in dielectric of solvents (moving from *n*-octanol to water), such sharp variation is not observed. Low electrophilicity of the Az⁺ ions might affect the acceptance of electron density from guanine (in DNA) (Scheme 1). This in turn weakens the tendency (measured in terms of interaction energy between the two species) of the Az⁺ ions to bind with guanine (in DNA) in solvent phases. To verify this, we calculated the interaction energies between Az⁺ ion and GC-base pair. The BSSE corrected interaction energies are reported in Table 1 and are calculated using super-molecular approach (for the sake of simplicity, we have considered only one GC base pair instead of the DNA chain). Interaction energy values clearly show a

Table 1. Gas and aqueous phase interaction energies (in kcal/mol) at B3LYP/6-31 + G(d) level of theory

Drug molecule	Interaction energy	
	Gas phase	Aqueous phase
Uracil mustard	-56.97	-25.20
Spiromustine	-52.71	-20.86
Chlorambucil	-50.40	-25.03
Mustine	-48.64	-23.08
Melphalan	-46.76	-34.96
Bendamustine	-44.56	-24.26

sharp drop as we move from gas to aqueous phase; thus supporting the above results. Trend of interaction energy in gas phase however does not tally with the aqueous phase trend indicating that the extent of solvation varies from species to species.

Thermochemical properties :

Thermodynamic feasibility of the Az⁺ ion formation process (drug → Az⁺ + Cl⁻), is observed from Δ*H* (change in enthalpy) and Δ*G* (change in Gibbs free energy) involved in the process at different temperatures as well as in different solvent media using supermolecular

approach (e.g. $\Delta H = (H_{\text{azi}^+} + H_{\text{Cl}^-}) - H_{\text{drug}}$).

Variations of ΔG and ΔH in different solvents at 298.15 K are summarised in Fig. 3. It is interesting to note that, as the dielectric constant of the medium increases (moving from gas phase to aqueous phase), ΔG and ΔH values drop suddenly (still exhibiting positive values), clearly indicating the effect of solvent polarity on both the parameters (Figs. 3(a) and 3(b)). It is conclusive to comment that the Az^+ ion formation is comparatively favourable in solvent phase compared to gas phase.

Our next step is to analyse the effect of temperature

(a) Variation of ΔH

(b) Variation of ΔG

Fig. 3. Variation of enthalpy (ΔH) and Gibbs free energy (ΔG) involved in aziridinium ion formation process from different drug molecules (all values are in kcal/mol) (■-gas phase, ●-*n*-octanol, ▲-1,2-ethanediol, ▼-water).

on the thermodynamic parameters. ΔG and ΔH for the ion formation process and are calculated at five different temperatures in gas and aqueous phases, shown in Figs. 4(a-d).

It is evident from Fig. 4 that as temperature increases, gas as well as aqueous phase ΔG drops significantly (Figs. 4(a-b)) whereas ΔH decreases slightly (Figs. 4(c-d)). It is to be worth mentioning that spiromustine exhibit exceptional behaviour in gas as well as in aqueous phase. Our observations suggest that the Az^+ ion formation is favoured at high temperature and polar solvents. As cytoplasm is a polar medium, this observation implies that the Az^+ ion formation is favoured in cytoplasm at normal body temperature.

NBO analysis :

The concept of natural bond orbital (NBO) analysis is helpful to study the distribution of electrons in atomic and molecular orbitals for the one-electron density matrix for defining the shape of the atomic orbitals in the molecular environment and then derive molecular bonds from electron density between atoms²⁰ and hence we have performed NBO analysis at B3LYP/6-31+G(d) level of theory.

The effect of substitution of the methyl group of mustine by electron withdrawing groups is observed from the calculated NBO charges on the drug molecules (carbon and nitrogen centers, 'a' in Scheme 1). The NBO charges at the N center of the drug is in the order : mustine (-0.5553) > bendamustine (-0.5545) > uracil mustard (-0.5491) > spiromustine (-0.5226) > chlorambucil (-0.5081) > melphalan (-0.4878). It is seen that all the drug molecules possess lesser negative charge on the N center compared to mustine. Thus, substitution at the N atom becomes successful in withdrawing electronic charges from N atom which is necessary to slow down the rate of Az^+ ion formation.

Conclusion

We have made an effort to study the reactivity, interaction energy and thermodynamics of Az^+ ions formation. Our study reveals that :

(i) Reactivity of the Az^+ ion intermediates lowered on incorporation of solvent media which in turn reduces

Fig. 4. Variation of enthalpy (ΔH) and Gibbs free energy (ΔG) (kcal/mol) with temperature (Kelvin) in gas and aqueous phases (∇ -spiromustine, \diamond -uracil mustard, \triangleleft -melphalan, \square -bendamustine, \circ -chlorambucil, Δ -mustine).

Scheme 1. Transfer of electron density from guanine to aziridinium ion during alkylation.

the capability of the species to accept electron density from guanine. Exceptional drop in electrophilicity of the Az^+ ions in polar solvent make them stable.

(ii) The Az^+ ion intermediates of the prototype drugs exhibit significant interaction energy with GC base pair in gas as well as in aqueous phases and is the chief key for their cytotoxicity.

(iii) High temperature and polarity of the solvent favours the thermodynamics of the Az^+ ion formation. Thus body temperature and polarity of cytoplasm allows formation of the Az^+ ion.

(iv) NBO analysis shows that substitution at the N atom may slow down the rate of Az^+ ion formation.

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References

1. S. R. Rajski and R. M. Williams, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 2723.
2. (a) S. Neidle and M. Waring, (eds.), "Molecular Aspects of Anti-cancer Drug Action", Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1994; (b) K. W. Kohn, "Anticancer Drugs", in : H. Tapiero, J. Robert and T. J. Lampidis (eds.), INSERM, John Libbey Eurotext, London, Paris, 1989.
3. D. M. Noll, T. M. Mason and P. S. Miller, *Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **106**, 277.
4. A. Hamza, H. Borch and D. Vasilescu, *J. Biomol. St. Dyn.*, 1996, **13**, 915.
5. B. Singer, *Nature*, 1976, **264**, 333.
6. D. T. Beranek, C. C. Weis and D. H. Swenson, *Carcinogenesis*, 1980, **1**, 595.
7. P. K. Shukla, P. C. Misra and S. Suhai, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2007, **449**, 323.
8. R. B. Silverman, "The Organic Chemistry of Drug Design and Drug Action", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Academic Press, 2004.
9. (a) P. K. Bhattacharyya and R. Kar, *Comput. Theoret. Chem.*, 2011, **967**, 5; (b) B. Neog, N. Sarmah, P. K. Bhattacharyya and R. Kar, *Comput. Theo. Chem.*, 2011, **976**, 60.
10. (a) P. Pérez, R. Contreras and A. Aizman, *J. Mol. Struct. : THEOCHEM*, 1997, **390**, 169; (b) R. Kar, K. R. S. Chandrakumar and S. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2007, **111**, 375; (c) R. Kar and S. Pal, *Int. J. Quant. Chem.*, 2009, **110**, 1642.
11. R. G. Parr and W. Yang, "Density-Functional Theory of Atoms and Molecules", Oxford University Press, New York, 1989.
12. (a) P. Geerlings, F. De Proft and W. Langenaekar, *Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **103**, 1793; (b) P. K. Chattaraj, U. Sarkar and D. R. Roy, *Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **106**, 2065; (c) H. S. De, S. Krishnamurty and S. Pal, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2009, **113**, 7101; (d) J. Moens, P. Geerlings and G. Roos, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2007, **13**, 8174; (e) G. Roos, P. Geerlings and J. Messens, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2009, **113**, 13465; (f) N. Barua, P. Sarmah, I. Hussain, R. C. Deka and A. K. Buragohain, *Chem. Biol. Drug Design*, 2012, **79**, 553; (g) P. Sarmah and R. C. Deka, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2011, **508**, 295; (h) N. Saikia and R. C. Deka, *Comput. Theo. Chem.*, 2011, **964**, 257; (i) N. Saikia and R. C. Deka, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2010, **500**, 65; (j) P. Sarmah and R. C. Deka, *J. Mol. Model*, 2010, **16**, 411.
13. R. G. Parr, R. A. Donnelly, M. Levy and W. E. Palke, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1978, **68**, 3801.
14. (a) R. G. Parr and R. G. Pearson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 7512; (b) R. G. Pearson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 6801.
15. T. A. Koopmans, *Physica*, 1933, **1**, 104.
16. R. G. Parr, L. V. Szentpaly and S. Liu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 1922.
17. (a) A. D. Becke, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 5648; (b) C. Lee, W. Yang and R. G. Parr, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1998, **37**, 785.
18. (a) B. Mennucci and J. Tomasi, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1997, **106**, 5151; (b) R. Cammi, B. Mennucci and J. Tomasi, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2000, **104**, 5631.
19. Gaussian 09, Revision B.01, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford CT, 2010.
20. F. Jensen, "Introduction to Computational Chemistry", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons Ltd., 2007.